

KERNEL DESIGN TECHNIQUES FOR ALIAS-FREE TIME-FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTIONS

John R. O'Hair and Bruce W. Suter

United States Air Force Institute of Technology
AFIT/ENG, 2950 P Street
Wright-Patterson AFB, OH 45433-7765

Abstract

This paper presents a modification of the Alias-Free Generalized Discrete Time-Frequency Distribution (AF-GDTFD) which reduces the computations necessary to implement the algorithm from $O(N^3)$ to $O(N^2 \log N)$. With this new implementation, we examine the problem of designing/modifying kernels defined in the ambiguity plane for use with the AF-GDTFD. We present three different methods to allow the use of these kernels and demonstrate them using the Butterworth kernel.

Introduction

Jeong and Williams introduced a generalized method to calculate an Alias-Free Generalized Discrete Time-Frequency Distribution (AF-GDTFD)[1,3]. It corrects for the inadvertent decimation in the lag direction of the standard discrete TFD which can result in aliasing. Their method relies on a modification of the sampling grid of the kernel.

The AF-GDTFD is an $O(N^3)$ process and requires the continuous form of a kernel in the time-lag domain be known. We detail the modifications made to the basic AF-GDTFD to decrease the computational complexity to $O(N^2 \log N)$ and allow the use of kernels designed in the ambiguity plane where the continuous form of the kernel in the time-lag domain is unavailable or difficult to obtain.

This paper is divided into four sections. First, a discussion of the AF-GDTFD as presented in [1]. Second, a description of the modifications made to create an $O(N^2 \log N)$ algorithm. Next, three methods to modify kernels designed in the ambiguity plane to the alias-free form are presented, and lastly, the three methods are compared.

Background

The Generalized Time-Frequency Distribution (GTFD) is given by Cohen [2] and for the Jeong and Williams implementation of the AF-GDTFD has the form

$$C(t, \omega; \phi) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \iint s(u + \frac{\tau}{2}) s^*(u - \frac{\tau}{2}) \psi(t - u, \tau) e^{-j\tau\omega} du d\tau \quad (1)$$

where

$$\psi(t, \tau) = \int \phi(\theta, \tau) e^{-j\theta t} d\theta$$

The common discrete form of equation (1) is given by

$$C(n, f; \phi) = \sum_{k=-N/4}^{N/4-1} \left(\sum_{t=-N/2}^{N/2-1} R_s(t, k) \psi(n-t, k) \right) e^{-\frac{j2\pi kf}{N}}$$

where $R_s(t, k) = s(t+k) s^*(t-k)$ and N is the number of samples.

We have samples of $s(\alpha)$ at every integer value of α , but the formulation of $R_s(t, k)$ only includes half of the possible products. In [1], Jeong and Williams note data is available whenever the argument of s is an integer, i.e. $t \pm k/2 \in \mathbb{Z}$. This suggests that we have data when k is even and t is an integer and when k is odd and t is an integer plus one-half. $R_s(t, k)$ can be thought of as lying on the hexagonally decimated rectangular grid (or hexagonal grid). This is a function which has been sampled at intervals of $1/2$ in t and k and then hexagonally decimate by a factor of four (see, for example, Vaidyanathan [4], p573).

If we take $R_s(t, k)$ on the hexagonal grid and use this instead of the rectangular grid, we are now using all of the signal, s , making the new distribution periodic in 2π . This is the basis of the Jeong and Williams method. Their discrete formulation is based upon appropriately discretizing (1) which involves convolving $R_s(t, k)$ and a hexagonally sampled form of $\psi(t, k)$ and taking its Fourier transform in the k direction.

A Faster AF-GDTFD

The method reported in [1] is an $O(N^3)$ process. With a slight modification, the AF-GDTFD can be implemented in $O(N^2 \log N)$ computations. The faster form is based upon the Cohen's class using the form

$$C(t, \omega; \phi) = \iint A(\theta, \tau) \phi(\theta, \tau) e^{-j\tau\omega - j\theta t} d\tau d\theta \quad (2)$$

where $A(t, \tau) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int s(u + \frac{\tau}{2}) s^*(u - \frac{\tau}{2}) e^{ju t} du$ is the

Ambiguity Function (AF).

If we discretize and periodize (2), we get

$$C(n, f; \phi) = \sum_{k, p = -\frac{N}{2}}^{N/2-1} \phi(p, k) A(p, k) e^{-\frac{j2\pi(pn + kf)}{N}} \quad (3)$$

$$A(p, k) = \sum_{u=-N/2}^{N/2} R_s(u, k) e^{j2\pi u p / N}$$

If N is restricted to powers of two, then using the FFT to implement (3) results in an $O(N^2 \log N)$ process.

One subtlety is encountered as a result of using the DFT. For the odd rows of the kernel, the sampling shifts for the kernel and the bilinear signal must be in opposite directions. i.e.

$$R_s(t, k) = \begin{cases} s(t + \frac{k}{2}) s(t - \frac{k}{2}) & k \text{ even} \\ s(t + \frac{k+1}{2}) s(t - \frac{k-1}{2}) & k \text{ odd} \end{cases}$$

and the kernel, $\phi(p, k)$, is the inverse Fourier transform in the p direction of a kernel function, ψ , defined in the t - k plane given by

$$\phi(n, k) = \begin{cases} \sum_{t=-N/2}^{N/2} \psi(t, k) e^{j2\pi t n / N} & k \text{ even} \\ \sum_{t=-N/2}^{N/2} \psi(t - \frac{1}{2}, k) e^{j2\pi t n / N} & k \text{ odd} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

We now have a discrete formulation which uses the complete sampling bandwidth and is 2π periodic instead of π periodic. Equation (3) can be implemented in $O(N^2 \log N)$ computations as compared to $O(N^3)$ computations for the method given in [1].

Methods to Design Alias-Free Kernels

One problem with the AF-GDTFD is the calculation of an appropriately sampled kernel, ψ . Often, it is convenient to design kernels in the ambiguity domain where the kernel acts as a two-dimensional multiplicative filter. That filter must be altered such that the values used are equivalent to the inverse Fourier transform of ψ on the hexagonal grid. We will call this the *shifted* $\phi(\theta, \tau)$.

Method 1 (The Continuous Form Method)

The most straight forward method of calculating the shifted $\phi(\theta, \tau)$ is to calculate the continuous $\phi(\theta, \tau)$, take its Fourier transform which yields the continuous function, ψ . The shifted $\phi(n, k)$ (note this is now discrete) is then found via equation (4).

The Butterworth kernel [5] demonstrates the difficulty that can arise using this method. The Butterworth kernel is given by

$$\phi(\theta, \tau) = \frac{1}{1 + (\theta/\theta_1)^{2N} (\tau/\tau_1)^{2M}} \quad (5)$$

where τ_1 and θ_1 are constants greater than zero and N and M are integers greater than zero. Using contour integration it is possible to show that the Fourier transform of (5) is

$$\psi(t, \tau) = 2\pi j \alpha \left(\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \frac{(z - z_k) e^{jz|t|}}{\alpha + z^{2N}} \Bigg|_{z=z_k} \right) \quad (6)$$

where

$$\alpha = \theta_1^{2N} \left(\frac{\tau_1}{\tau} \right)^{2M} \quad \text{and} \quad z_k = \theta_1 \left(\frac{\tau_1}{\tau} \right)^{M/N} e^{j\pi(2k+1)/2N}$$

While this can be bothersome to calculate in practice, it does have a closed form solution. The problem occurs when we sample $\psi(t, \tau)$ and take the inverse discrete Fourier transform. Since neither (5) or (6) are compact, sampling the waveforms with a finite number of points over a finite window is going to introduce error. It is, therefore, not likely that the shifted $\phi(n, k)$ can be accurately determined by hexagonally sampling $\psi(t, \tau)$, especially for small values of N .

Also note, if a closed form solution to the continuous Fourier transform does not exist, this method will not work. It will also not work for TFD's where the kernel is adapted to the signal frame by frame. In this instance, the continuous form $\phi(\theta, \tau)$ is unknown and, therefore, $\psi(t, \tau)$ cannot be calculated.

Method 2 (Interpolation Method)

The second method approaches the problem of finding the shifted $\phi(n, k)$ in a different manner. Note from (1) we are actually performing a convolution of a kernel defined in t - τ with the rotated outer product of the signal. Computationally, the fastest way to do this is via the fast Fourier transform and circular convolution, but we are still performing a convolution. Let a given even indexed row of the rotated outer product of the signal be represented by $X[k]$, an odd indexed row be represented by $X[k+1/2]$. Further let both the even and odd indexed row of the kernel be given by $Y[k]$. What is the result of the convolution of the even rows and odd rows?

$$X[k] * Y[k] = \mathcal{F}[x[n]y[n]] = Z[k] \quad \text{even rows}$$

$$\begin{aligned} X\left[k + \frac{1}{2}\right] * Y[k] &= \mathcal{F}[e^{-j\pi n/N} x[n]y[n]] \\ &= \mathcal{F}[e^{-j\pi n/N} z[n]] = Z\left[k + \frac{1}{2}\right] \quad \text{odd rows} \end{aligned}$$

From this we see the result of not calculating the shifted $\phi(n, k)$ is the convolution of the rotated outer product of the signal and kernel will still be on the hexagonally decimated rectangular grid.

We can exploit this structure by interpolating to fill in the missing elements, take the Fourier transform along τ and create a TFD which is 2π periodic and has twice the sampling density in time. This method generates a TFD using all of the outer product terms of the signal and as a result the distribution does not suffer aliasing up to the

Nyquist frequency.

With two dimensional interpolation, we do lose some time and frequency resolution for rapidly changing signals. In the worst case of an impulse or pure tone, the localization of a feature in the time-frequency plane can decrease by as much 50 percent.

Method 3 (Phase Shift Method)

Another method which could be used to find the shifted $\phi(n,k)$ is to sample $\phi(\theta,\tau)$ on a rectangular grid at intervals of $1/2$ along θ for τ odd, take its discrete Fourier transform and decimate the result. This is equivalent to having sampled $\psi(t,\tau = \text{odd integer})$ at intervals of $1/2$. If ψ is decimated by taking the odd indexed samples (i.e. $\psi(t=0.5, \tau = \text{odd integer}), \psi(t = 1.5, \tau = \text{odd integer}), \dots$) and take the inverse DFT of the resulting sequence. The result is the shifted $\phi(n,k)$.

This method is exactly equivalent to the well known transform relationship,

$$e^{j2\pi ln/N} x[n] \leftrightarrow X[k-l],$$

where $x[n] \leftrightarrow X[k]$ are a Fourier transform pair. As a result, we will call this the phase shift method. In practice, we use the phase shift relationship rather than decimating the oversampled DFT and inverting as the phase shift is $O(N)$ as compared to $O(N \log N)$ of the decimated DFT.

With $l=0.5$, the shifted $\phi(n,k)$ can be easily be determined by starting with the unshifted $\phi(n,k)$ and modifying that as follows:

$$\phi(n,k) = \begin{cases} \phi(n,k) & k \text{ even} \\ e^{j\pi n/N} \phi(n,k) & k \text{ odd} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

However, this method is only approximately equal to the shifted $\phi(n,k)$ found by (4) and is dependent upon the size of N . As N increases, the difference between (4) and (7) decreases. The error is $O(1/N)$, but even for N as low as 128, the effect on the TFD is minor.

Comparison of Methods

To demonstrate the differences between the methods discussed above, examine the result of applying each method to the Butterworth kernel given by (5) and calculating the AF-GDTFD of a multicomponent signal. Let the signal consists of two tones, one at 0.136π and the other at 0.777π , two impulses at $t = 0.25$ and $t = 0.625$, and a rising chirp starting at 0.18π with a slope of 0.562π .

If we let $\theta_1 = \tau_1 = 10.0$ and $M = N = 1$, by Method 1, we determine the kernel in the time-lag domain to be

$$\psi(t,k) = \frac{100\pi}{k} e^{-100t/k}$$

If we sample this as we would in (4), the TFD which results is shown in Figure 1. Compare this result to the TFD generated by the shifted kernel calculated via Method 3. Here, the kernel is calculated in the ambiguity plane by

sampling (5) and applying a phase shift as given by (7). (See Figure 2.)

Although the continuous forms of the Butterworth kernel in the Time-Lag domain and ambiguity plane are equivalent in calculating the continuous TFD, when they are sampled and windowed that relationship no longer holds; hence, the TFD's shown in Figure 1 and 2 are actually two different TFD's which will approach each other as the size of the window and the density of the sampling go up.

The second method produces a TFD shown in Figure 3. In this case, we used a weighted linear interpolation based on the four nearest neighbors. Because we are interpolating a hexagonally decimated function, we will produce a TFD with twice as many points in the time direction. This is reflected in the increased width of Figure 3; however, the time support remains the same (i.e. 0 to 1.0).

As expected, the tones and impulses are more difficult to detect and are somewhat less localized in the Interpolated AF-GDTFD than they are in either the Jeong-Williams AF-GDTFD or phase shifted AF-GDTFD.

Method one is the most accurate of the three methods in determining the outcome of the interpolation; however, it has the major drawback of requiring the continuous form of the kernel in the time-lag domain. Also, the sampled $\psi(t,\tau)$ is not necessarily the DFT of the sampled $\phi(\theta,\tau)$ indicating we have actually changed kernels. In addition, it is often impractical or impossible to obtain the continuous form (e.g. optimal kernels created and modified in the ambiguity plane). Method one is, therefore, not a viable solution to the problem of designing alias free kernels in the ambiguity plane.

Method two has problems previously mention in regard to loss of localization in time as well as imposing extra low pass filtering in the frequency domain. Also, it requires an additional $O(N^2)$ computations to implement for even the simple interpolation described above. It is, thus, not an ideal choice for designing alias free kernels.

The most useful of the three methods is the third. It provides a reasonably accurate estimate of the shifted $\phi(n,k)$ providing a TFD very similar to that produced by method one. Because it does not suffer the problems associated with method two and does not require the continuous form of the kernel in the time-lag, this is the best of the three methods for calculating the alias free form of a kernel designed in the ambiguity plane.

Conclusion

In this paper, we presented a method to reduce the computations necessary to calculate the AF-GDTFD from $O(N^3)$ to $O(N^2 \log N)$. We further extended this algorithm to allow kernels designed and implemented in the ambigu-

ity plane to be modified so they can be used to calculate the AF-GDTFD by the faster method. The new method has the advantage of being simple to implement, producing accurate results and most importantly allowing the design of kernels in the ambiguity plane without needing to calculate the continuous form of the kernel in the time-lag domain.

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Figure 1. AF-GDTFD via Jeong-Williams Method

Figure 2. AF-GDTFD via Phase Shift Method

Figure 3. AF-GDTFD via Interpolation Method